

Anharmonic effects revealed by temperature-dependent phonon lifetimes and thermal conductivities in a p-conjugated molecular crystal

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ABSTRACT

Anharmonicity plays a central role in many key phenomena in solids. Here, we investigate its impact in the organic semiconductor [1]benzothieno[3,2-b]-benzothiophene (BTBT), whose Raman spectra exhibit signatures of phonon mixing revealed by polarization-dependent measurements. Using molecular dynamics simulations, we compute the spectral energy density to reproduce the experimentally observed temperature-dependent phonon frequencies and lifetimes.

To quantify interactions between vibrational modes, we introduce cross-correlation analysis as a tool to characterize phonon mixing across temperatures, revealing that mode coupling persists even at low temperatures. We further explore how these anharmonic effects influence macroscopic thermal transport. Because the thermal conductivity of anharmonic organic semiconductors cannot be captured by the particle-like Peierls–Boltzmann formalism, we solve the Wigner Transport Equation to account for phonon wavelike tunneling effects. Our results show that wave-like transport dominates thermal conductivity, leading to a temperature-activated conductivity along all crystallographic directions, a trend also confirmed by approach-to-equilibrium molecular dynamics simulations.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, organic semiconductors (OSCs) have attracted considerable attention owing to their wide range of technological applications, including organic field-effect transistors¹ and organic solar cells². While their electronic and optical properties have been extensively investigated, their thermal behavior has received comparatively less attention. Thermal behavior is of particular importance for emerging technologies such as thermoelectric devices^{3,4}. In this context, accurate evaluation of thermal conductivity is crucial both for guiding practical device optimization and for advancing fundamental insight into heat transport mechanisms at the microscopic level.

Some organic semiconductors feature physical properties that are strongly influenced by the anharmonic character of atomic vibrations, which must therefore be explicitly considered in simulations^{5–7}. Anharmonicity is responsible for a wide range of solid-state phenomena, including thermal expansion, heat transport, the temperature dependence of phonon frequencies, finite phonon lifetimes, and phonon–phonon interactions⁸. One common approach to account for

anharmonicity is the explicit calculation of interatomic force constants of order higher than second. This method allows for systematic inclusion of anharmonic effects, but it is restricted to a certain order of anharmonicity. For example, in the standard perturbative description of heat transport, a second-order heat-flux expression is combined with third-order anharmonic interactions.

Molecular dynamics (MD) techniques, such as normal mode decomposition technique⁹, offer an alternative approach to the explicit computation of anharmonic force constants for assessing anharmonic effects. These methods extract anharmonic effects directly from the atomic trajectories, thereby accounting for anharmonicity to all orders. Their main limitations are the high computational cost, since long simulations are required for convergence, the need for accurate force fields and the fact that it is governed by equipartition, as MD is inherently classical¹⁰.

Recent studies have demonstrated that some prototypical molecular crystals exhibit high-order anharmonic effects. In particular, [1]benzothieno[3,2-b]-benzothiophene (BTBT) displays temperature-dependent vibrational frequencies from Raman spectra, an effect usually referred to as quasi-harmonic as caused by an expansion of the lattice with increasing temperature. Polarized Raman measurements have further suggested the occurrence of phonon mixing in BTBT¹¹. We consider this to be a more profound manifestation of anharmonicity, as this requires abandoning the view of independent harmonic oscillators.

As other molecular crystals bonded by weak Van der Waals forces, BTBT exhibits large atomic displacements from equilibrium⁵. For this reason, molecular dynamics methods are particularly suitable for its study, since strong anharmonicity is described more conveniently by sampling real atomic trajectories rather than relying on perturbative approaches. Among these, the normal mode decomposition technique⁹ enables the extraction of both temperature-dependent vibrational

frequencies and phonon lifetimes. This is achieved by calculating the power spectrum of the atomic velocities projected onto phonon eigenvectors:

$$G_{qs}(\omega) = 2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \langle v_{q,s}^*(0) | v_{q,s}(t) \rangle e^{i\omega t} dt \approx \frac{\langle |v_{qs}(t)|^2 \rangle}{\frac{1}{2} \gamma_{qs} \pi \left(1 + \left(\frac{\omega - \tilde{\omega}_{qs}}{\frac{1}{2} \gamma_{qs}} \right)^2 \right)} \quad (1)$$

where $v_{q,s}$ is the atomic velocity projected onto phonon branch s and wave-vector q , $\tilde{\omega}_{qs}$ is the renormalized phonon frequency and γ_{qs} is the phonon linewidth. In this model, we describe the decay of the phonon-mode-projected velocity autocorrelation function using a damped harmonic oscillator formalism, which represents the relaxation dynamics. Consequently, its Fourier transform can be approximated by a Lorentzian function, yielding for each phonon a temperature-dependent frequency ($\tilde{\omega}_{qs}$) from the peak position and a linewidth (γ_{qs}) from the full width at half maximum. The resulting expression in Equation (1) corresponds to the spectral energy density (SED). Phonon mixing can then be identified through overlapping Lorentzian peaks, which in the SED appear as blurred profiles¹². In the harmonic limit, the SED would reproduce the harmonic phonon dispersion, whereas in anharmonic systems the Lorentzian functions overlap, leading to the blurring of the SED profiles. The SED can therefore serve as a practical tool for analyzing phonon mixing.

While the SED is useful for identifying phonon mixing, it does not provide a quantitative measure. In this work, we introduce the novel concept of cross-correlations as a tool to study phonon mixing. Our approach consists in calculating the Fourier transform of the cross-correlation of atomic velocities projected onto two different phonon modes:

$$G_{q_1, q_2, s}(\omega) = 2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \langle v_{q_1, s_1}^*(0) | v_{q_2, s_2}(t) \rangle e^{i\omega t} dt \quad (2)$$

where s_1 and s_2 are two different phonon branches. This corresponds to a full matrix of correlations $G_{q_1, q_2, s}$ where the autocorrelations are the diagonal terms and the cross-correlations are the off-diagonal terms. Cross-correlations enable the quantitative analysis of phonon mixing during the molecular dynamic runs. In the harmonic limit, where all the phonon modes are decoupled, the cross-correlations vanish, as projections over independent modes are not correlated. Non-zero values therefore indicate phonon mixing and offer a quantitative measure of the mixing.

Anharmonic effects may affect the macroscopic properties of OSCs, with thermal conductivity providing the most obvious manifestation. Two main approaches are commonly applied to compute thermal transport in crystals. The first is based on molecular dynamics (MD), with methods such as approach-to-equilibrium MD (AEMD)¹³⁻¹⁵, non-equilibrium MD (NEMD)¹⁶ and Green-Kubo type equilibrium MD¹⁷. These techniques use MD trajectories to simulate heat currents and thereby account explicitly for anharmonicity. Although MD captures anharmonicity, it does not naturally expose microscopic phonon transport mechanisms without additional analysis. The second approach to compute thermal conductivity in crystals is based on the Boltzmann Transport Equation (BTE)¹⁸, which breaks down when the interband spacing is smaller than the phonon linewidths, a situation common in OSCs. The recently developed Wigner Transport Equation (WTE) generalizes the BTE¹⁹, both in crystals and amorphous solids²⁰. While the BTE only accounts for particle-like transport, the WTE includes wave-like transport (in its coherence contribution to thermal conductivity), accounting for transport arising from the tunneling between different phonon modes. This coherence mechanism has proven essential for explaining the thermal conductivity of highly anharmonic materials²⁰. Since the coherence term reflects phonon mixing, we investigate its relationship with the cross-correlations introduced above.

Here, anharmonic effects are analyzed in detail using the normal-mode decomposition technique, which yields temperature-dependent phonon dispersions and spectral energy densities in excellent agreement with experimental Raman data for the active modes. We also investigate the temperature dependence of the cross-correlations, finding that they become sizeable as we move away from the harmonic limit at low temperature and represent an important contribution at room temperature. Thermal conductivity is then evaluated using the Wigner formalism with MD-derived linewidths, the BTE with third-order anharmonicity, and the AEMD method. We show that, at room temperature, the coherence contribution is the dominant component of the conductivity and that AEMD captures this effect, in agreement with the WTE. This is similar to what has been found in other OSCs, like naphthalene²¹. We further perform an anharmonicity sensitivity analysis by artificially varying phonon linewidths, showing that anharmonicity limits thermal conductivity at both low and room temperatures. Finally, we establish a qualitative connection between cross-correlations and Wigner's coherence contribution.

RESULTS

Harmonic and renormalized band structures

Our study focuses on BTBT, a π -conjugated molecular crystal containing two molecules per unit cell and belonging to the low-symmetry space group $P2_1/c$ containing 48 atoms per unit cell. Details of the crystal structure employed here are provided in Supplementary Figure 1 and the lattice parameters are provided in Supplementary Table 1. The first step of our methodology involves the calculation of atomic forces. While such forces are typically obtained from *ab initio* methods such as density functional theory (DFT), this approach is impractical for molecular crystals such as BTBT, as the calculations would have a computational cost prohibitively high for standard plane-wave codes. Therefore, it is needed to use computationally cheaper methods such

as classical force fields. We use the GAFF force field^{22,23} to compute forces throughout this work. Validation against phonon densities of states obtained from DFT calculations (Supplementary Figure 2) confirms that GAFF provides an acceptable compromise between accuracy and efficiency in this case.

We first computed the quasi-harmonic phonon dispersion of BTBT at finite temperature, using the experimental cells¹¹ measured at temperatures ranging from 100 to 300 K, and allowing all atoms to relax while keeping the volume of the cell fixed to match the experimental data. For these calculations, we used the Phonopy^{24,25} code and a 2x4x4 supercell containing 1536 atoms. From these calculations, we obtained harmonic force constants and corresponding phonon dispersions, shown in Figure 1a for 100 and 300 K. Dispersions at additional temperatures are shown in Supplementary Figure 3. As expected, the band structures at low and room temperature exhibit the same overall shape, with slightly lower frequencies at room temperature due to thermal expansion. The absence of imaginary frequencies confirms the structural stability, and this phonon dispersion is used in all subsequent calculations.

To capture anharmonic effects beyond the quasi-harmonic approximation, we performed MD simulations of BTBT at different temperatures and extracted effective finite-temperature force constants. The renormalized phonon dispersion at finite temperature is shown in Figure 1b (additional temperatures are shown in Supplementary Figure 4), while Supplementary Figure 5 shows the convergence of the renormalized frequencies and lifetimes with respect to simulation time. The effect of renormalization is more pronounced at room temperature, where anharmonicity is stronger, than at low temperature. In contrast to the uniform redshift caused by thermal expansion, renormalization produces mode-dependent frequency shifts: intermolecular modes are more strongly affected than intramolecular ones, consistent with the weaker intermolecular forces⁵.

As the temperature decreases, the renormalized dispersion gradually converges to the harmonic phonon dispersion, reflecting the diminishing role of anharmonicity. This is discussed further in Supplementary Section 3.2, where the phonon dispersion is calculated at ultralow temperature (20 K).

Figure 1. a) Quasi-harmonic phonon dispersion of BTBT at 100 K and 300 K. All modes decrease in frequency at 300 K due to lattice expansion. b) Renormalized phonon dispersion at 100 K and 300 K. At 100 K, the renormalized bands are nearly identical to the harmonic dispersion owing to weak anharmonicity, while at room temperature the differences are more pronounced. For clarity, only modes below 6 THz are shown.

Spectral energy density and comparison to experimental data

The SED (Equation 1) was obtained by fitting the power spectrum to Lorentzian functions. Figure 2 shows the SED at different temperatures. At low temperature (100 K) anharmonicity is reduced compared to room temperature, leading to narrower linewidths and less overlap between phonon branches. As temperature rises, anharmonicity broadens the linewidths, leading to overlap between the Lorentzian functions. This overlap enables phonon mixing and blurs the SED profiles, as seen at 200 K and most prominently at room temperature, where the bands are hardly distinguishable. This behavior is similar to what has been reported in the case of lead halide perovskites, where the importance of anharmonicity is well documented¹². These results indicate

that phonon mixing is weak at low temperature and significant at room temperature. Consistently, cross-correlations are expected to follow the same trend, vanishing as temperature decreases and becoming important at room temperature. Likewise, the coherence term in the Wigner thermal conductivity is expected to provide the dominant contribution at room temperature.

Figure 2. Spectral energy density at 100 K, 200 K and 300 K. Black dots are the quasi-harmonic phonon dispersion at each temperature, included for comparison. At low temperature the band structure of BTBT is still visible, whereas at 300K it is completely blurred.

Individual phonon frequencies and lifetimes were obtained from the SED and compared with experimental data for the first Raman-active mode¹¹ (Figure 3). At low temperature (100 K), anharmonicity is weak, and renormalization has little effect: both the quasi-harmonic and renormalized frequencies reproduce the experimental value. With increasing temperature, the quasi-harmonic approximation fails to capture the temperature dependence of the frequencies, while the renormalized values remain in excellent agreement with experiment. This confirms the anharmonic character of BTBT and highlights the need to go beyond the quasi-harmonic approximation to accurately describe phonon frequencies.

Lifetimes for the first Raman active mode are also shown in Figure 3. The calculations reproduce reasonably well the temperature dependence considering the experimental resolution. Comparison

with higher Raman-active modes is shown in Supplementary Figure 7 and Supplementary Figure 8 and shows trends similar to those obtained for the first mode. These lifetimes are similar in order of magnitude at room temperature to those found on acenes²¹ and an order of magnitude larger than those typically found in lead halide perovskites such as MAPbI₃ or MAPbBr₃²⁶.

Figure 3. Comparison between the quasi-harmonic, renormalized and experimental frequency of the first Raman active mode (left) and lifetime (right) at different temperatures.

Phonon mixing analysis: cross-correlations

Phonon-phonon correlations of BTBT were computed at the Γ point using Equation 2 and are displayed as temperature-dependent heatmaps in Figure 4. The diagonal represents auto-correlations, while the off-diagonal terms represent cross-correlations. Since cross-correlations measure phonon mixing, they should only be significant when phonon linewidths overlap, as indicated by blurred SED profiles. The results are in line with that expectation: at 20 K, cross-correlations vanish; at 100 K, they emerge between pseudo-degenerate low-frequency modes; and at room temperature, extensive mode–mode correlations appear. This temperature dependence parallels the behavior of Wigner’s coherence contribution to thermal conductivity.

These results establish cross-correlations as a useful measurement of mode–mode coupling. While no formal justification has been derived, the orthogonality of phonon eigenvectors explains why cross-correlations vanish when modes do not mix during the dynamics. Non-zero cross-correlations are found predominantly between modes of similar frequency, consistent with overlapping SED profiles.

Figure 4. Cross correlations (divided by $k_B T$, where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, to normalize the scale) at temperatures ranging from 20 K up to 300 K. Only cross-correlations between the 23 lowest-frequency non-acoustic modes are computed. At 20 K the cross-correlations are zero, whereas they become relevant as temperature increases up to room temperature.

Thermal conductivity

Having established the importance of anharmonicity in BTBT, we now compute the thermal conductivity using the WTE. Formally, the Wigner transport equation is derived relying on the standard perturbative treatment of anharmonicity, which involves a heat-flux expression

combining harmonic (second-order) frequencies and velocity operators, and third-order anharmonic linewidths¹⁹. Because the linewidths we obtained from MD are in reasonable agreement with the experimental ones, here we phenomenologically combine the WTE with MD-derived fully anharmonic (infinite-order) linewidths. We find that the Wigner thermal conductivity is converged with respect to the MD simulation time used to compute the linewidths (Supplementary Figure 6). We also evaluate the impact of using MD-derived fully anharmonic frequencies and velocity operators in the WTE (data in Supplementary Table 2 and Supplementary Figure 9) and find that this leads to only minor variations in the thermal conductivity. The Wigner thermal conductivity along the three crystallographic directions is shown in Figures 5a–c, with the contributions from particle-like (Boltzmann) propagative mechanisms and wavelike tunneling (coherence) mechanisms displayed separately. The results indicate that the coherence term contributes significantly even at 100 K and becomes the dominant contribution at room temperature. This trend is consistent with the blurring of SED profiles and the emergence of cross-correlations as temperature increases. The population (Boltzmann) term follows the expected $1/T$ dependence, while the coherence term compensates for this decrease, resulting in an overall upward trend in the total conductivity at high temperature. This behavior has been reported in other materials²¹ and is observed here in all three crystallographic directions. Along the interlayer (x -axis) direction, the change in trend occurs near 200 K, whereas in the intralayer directions it appears closer to room temperature. This indicates that anharmonicity is stronger along the interlayer direction. Our computed thermal conductivity in the interlayer direction of BTBT, $0.60 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, is in excellent agreement with the only available experimental measurement ($0.63 \pm 0.12 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)²⁷.

In addition to the Wigner conductivity calculations, we also evaluated the thermal conductivity in the interlayer direction using the approach-to-equilibrium molecular dynamics (AEMD) method (Figure 5d). AEMD captures the increase in conductivity at high temperatures and matches the Wigner values above room temperature, confirming the compatibility between the quantum-accurate WTE method and classical AEMD at high temperatures. At low temperatures, however, AEMD yields higher conductivity. This discrepancy arises because AEMD employs the classical Dulong–Petit heat capacity, which is overestimated below room temperature (as Debye’s temperature is approached) and therefore leads to an overestimation of the conductivity in this regime.

To investigate the impact of anharmonicity beyond third order, we calculated the thermal conductivity within the BTE formalism using linewidths derived from third-order force constants and compared the results with population conductivities obtained from MD linewidths. The comparison for all three crystallographic directions is presented in Supplementary Figure 10. While the BTE values are nearly identical to the Wigner conductivities in the intralayer directions, the interlayer direction shows a systematic difference of about $0.1 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. This indicates that higher-order anharmonicity is only important in the interlayer direction, consistent with anharmonicity being stronger in this direction. In addition, the close agreement between the BTE conductivity obtained from third-order linewidths and the Wigner population term derived from MD linewidths supports our phenomenological approximation of using the MD-derived linewidths in the WTE calculations.

Figure 5. (a-c) xx, yy and zz components of the thermal conductivity tensor as a function of temperature. Green is the populations (Boltzmann) κ_p contribution, blue is the coherences κ_C contribution and black is the total conductivity. The green dotted line is the fitting of the populations, showing the $\kappa \propto 1/T$ dependence universally emerging from BTE theory with third-order linewidths in the high-temperature limit. (d) Comparison between AEMD and Wigner calculations for the interlayer (xx) thermal conductivity.

To further investigate how anharmonicity influences transport, we performed Wigner thermal conductivity calculations with artificially scaled linewidths²⁸. Figure 6 shows the conductivity obtained after increasing or reducing the linewidths by scaling factors of 2/3 and 3/2, respectively. At low temperature, classical particle-like transport is the dominant heat-conduction mechanism. Since the particle-like contribution is inversely proportional to the phonon linewidths, an artificial increase (decrease) of the linewidths leads to a decrease (increase) of both the particle-like and total thermal conductivity. At high temperatures, heat transport is instead dominated by wave-like

tunneling, which in this material is enhanced by an increase in the linewidths. Consequently, at high temperatures, increasing (decreasing) the linewidths results in an increase (decrease) of the total conductivity. In contrast, near the temperature at which the total conductivity reaches a minimum (around room temperature), where particle-like and wave-like transport coexist, an increase or decrease of the linewidth does not result in a change of the total conductivity. This behaviour arises from a compensation mechanism: broader linewidths reduce the particle-like contribution while simultaneously enhancing the wave-like contribution. These results show that the anharmonicity plays critical and opposite roles in governing the thermal conductivity at very low and at very high temperatures, while it has a negligible effect around room temperature where the opposite mechanisms compensate.

Figure 6. Thermal conductivity along the three crystallographic directions with linewidths artificially enlarged or reduced by a factor of 3/2 and 2/3, respectively. Shaded areas indicate the range of conductivities obtained with intermediate scaling factors. Conductivity is most sensitive to linewidths at low and high temperatures, while at room temperature the population and coherence contributions compensate.

As discussed above, coherence contribution is essential for accurately describing the thermal conductivity of BTBT, even at low temperature. The total coherence contribution can be decomposed into individual phonon-phonon contributions. The two-dimensional density of states

of the coherence contribution at different temperatures (Figure 7) shows that at 100 K the main contributions originate from couplings between similar-frequency modes, particularly quasi-degenerate ones. At room temperature, stronger anharmonicity enables couplings between a broader set of modes. This trend parallels the temperature dependence of the cross-correlations, supporting their qualitative interpretation as a measure of mode–mode coupling from MD trajectories. The same trend is consistent with the SED: at room temperature, where linewidths overlap, phonon coupling is allowed.

Figure 7. Two-dimensional density of states of the coherences' contribution to thermal conductivity as a function of frequencies at 100 K and 300 K.

DISCUSSION

In this work, we have investigated the strong anharmonicity of the prototypical molecular crystal BTBT, for which experimental studies have reported red shifts in Raman spectra with increasing temperature and indications of phonon mixing from polarized Raman measurements. Our objective was to understand phonon mixing in this system and characterize anharmonicity and how it influences thermal transport. MD is particularly well suited for this purpose, as it captures anharmonic effects to all orders. By combining MD with the normal-mode decomposition

technique, we reproduced the observed frequency red shifts and obtained accurate phonon lifetimes.

To investigate mode mixing, we computed the SED at different temperatures. The blurring of the SED profiles provides a direct indication of phonon mixing. In addition, we introduced cross-correlations as a quantitative framework to identify mode-mixing. We find that mixing is restricted to modes close in frequency, corresponding to those with overlapping linewidths in the SED. At the same time, the renormalized frequencies and lifetimes extracted from the SED are in excellent agreement with experimental data.

Due to its high anharmonicity, the thermal conductivity of BTBT cannot be described with the standard Peierls-Boltzmann particle-like formalism. Instead, using the Wigner Transport Equation shows that the coherence term, associated with wave-like transport, is the dominant contribution. This wave-like channel grows in strength with temperature and is sufficient to reverse the usual $1/T$ conductivity dependence, leading to an overall increase of total conductivity with T above 200-300K. In addition, this approach reproduces the experimental thermal conductivity at room temperature. The two-dimensional density of states of the coherences mirrors the cross-correlations, with contributions between modes of similar frequency. Complementary calculations with approach-to-equilibrium molecular dynamics (AEMD^{14,15}) also capture the upward trend and agree with the Wigner conductivity at room temperature and above.

CONCLUSIONS

We have performed a detailed analysis of microscopic anharmonicity in a prototypical molecular organic semiconductor and have shown that MD simulations with an accurate force field is capable of revealing anharmonic effects. Cross-correlations are used to quantify phonon mixing and behave similarly to the coherence's contribution to thermal conductivity. Our results also show

that the coherence contribution is crucial to understand the thermal conductivity of BTBT. Furthermore, this causes thermal conductivity to have a minimum around room temperature. This behavior originates from the dual role of anharmonicity in this material, which affects heat transport in opposite ways at low and high temperatures. At low temperature, anharmonicity limits heat transport due to the dominance of particle-like transport, while at high temperature it enhances transport as wave-like tunneling becomes dominant. This non-monotonic impact of anharmonicity on heat transport gives rise to an intermediate regime around room temperature, where particle-like and wave-like mechanisms coexist and compensate, resulting in the effects of anharmonicity cancelling out in the total thermal conductivity.

METHODS

Details on the molecular dynamics

Molecular dynamics were performed with LAMMPS²⁹ using an NVT ensemble, using periodical boundary conditions and a 2x4x4 supercell containing 1536 atoms. This supercell matches the cell used for phonon calculations. The timestep used was 1 fs and we used 25 ps of equilibrium time and 150 ps of production time for all quantities (renormalized frequencies, lifetimes, SED, cross-correlations) at all temperatures except 20 K, where we used 50 ps of equilibrium time to allow the system to fully relax.

Details on the calculation of second order harmonic force constants

Second order force constants were calculated using the finite-difference method implemented in phonoLAMMPS³⁰, which interfaces with Phonopy^{24,25}, using atomic displacement of 0.01 Å. Before computing the force constants, the atomic positions were relaxed using a threshold of 10^{-10} eV/Å, while maintaining the lattice parameters frozen to reproduce the experimental cells.

Details on the spectral energy density and cross-correlations

To compute the Fourier transform of the projected atomic velocities we used the Fast Fourier Transform algorithm as implemented in DynaPhoPy³¹.

Details on the Wigner thermal conductivity

Wigner thermal conductivity was computed solving the Wigner transport equation with a custom using the harmonic force constants derived from phonoLAMMPS in a 2x4x4 supercell. Linewidths were obtained from DynaPhoPy while isotopic linewidths were computed using Phono3py^{25,32}. The integral over the first Brillouin zone to compute the coherence term of the Wigner conductivity was evaluated over a 5x11x11 mesh, large enough to achieve convergence.

Details on AEMD and BTE + 3rd order force constants

Thermal conductivity from molecular dynamics simulations was computed via the Approach-to-Equilibrium Molecular Dynamics (AEMD) technique^{14,15}. We considered a supercell under periodic boundary conditions: the system is initially divided into two regions kept at two different temperatures T_H and T_C along the z -direction, with an initial $\Delta T(0) = T_H(0) - T_C(0) = 50K$. Under the assumption of no internal heat sources or sinks, and neglecting the presence of convective transport, the relaxation of this temperature difference follows the analytical solution of the one-dimensional heat diffusion equation:

$$\langle \Delta T(t) \rangle = \langle T_H(t) \rangle - \langle T_C(t) \rangle = \frac{8\langle \Delta T(0) \rangle}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2n+1} e^{-\beta^2 \bar{k} t}$$

Where $\beta = \pi n/L_z$, and \bar{k} is the thermal diffusivity, related to thermal conductivity via $\kappa = \bar{k}\rho C_V$, where ρ is the mass density of the system and C_V its specific heat that was calculated using the Dulong-Petit law. To implement the above equation, the two halves of the system are equilibrated separately in the NVT ensemble at the target hot and cold temperatures for 20 ps. Then, the system is allowed to evolve during a NVE run for 20 ns. The average temperature

difference from the NVE simulation is fitted using the previously introduced solution of the heat equation, using the thermal diffusivity as the fitting parameter. Our supercell has a cross-section of 225 nm^2 . Furthermore, since in non-equilibrium MD, thermal conductivity might be affected by size effect, we considered systems with increasing L_z , ranging from 10 to 60 nm and involving a number of atoms between 23520 and 117600, in order to obtain the infinite length limit using the $1/k$ vs $1/L_z$ extrapolation as illustrated in ^{33,34}. All AEMD simulations were carried using the LAMMPS package and adopted the same potential as the calculations described above.

3rd order anharmonic properties were obtained by solving the Boltzmann Transport Equation (BTE) using the κ ALDo code³⁵. κ ALDo computes phonon transport properties using the finite displacement method, which estimates interatomic force constants (IFCs) by considering harmonic and anharmonic lattice vibrations, to diagonalize the dynamical matrix and solve the BTE. In this case, we constructed a $2 \times 4 \times 4$ supercell and sampled the Brillouin zone with a $3 \times 6 \times 6$ \mathbf{q} -point mesh to extract harmonic and anharmonic force constants; these were then fed into the κ ALDo package to obtain the phonon dispersion relations and to solve the BTE using the direct inversion method, yielding the thermal conductivity.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Structure details of the crystal structure of the BTBT crystal, validation of the GAFF force field against first-principles calculations, quasi-harmonic and renormalized phonon dispersion at the full range of temperatures, details on the convergence of the renormalized phonon frequencies, phonon lifetimes and thermal conductivity with respect to MD simulation time, comparison with the experimental data for the second and third Raman active modes, analysis of the effect of the frequency renormalization on the thermal conductivity, and comparison with the thermal

conductivity computed with the BTE and linewidths derived from third-order force constants (PDF).

DATA AVAILABILITY

Raw data of BTBT crystal structures, molecular dynamics trajectories, force constants and post-processing scripts are available upon reasonable request to the authors.

CODE AVAILABILITY

LAMMPS is available at www.lammps.org²⁹; PhonoLAMMPS³⁰ is available at <https://github.com/abelcarreras/phonolammps>; DynaPhoPy is available at <https://abelcarreras.github.io/DynaPhoPy/>³¹; Phonopy^{24,25} is available at <https://phonopy.github.io/phonopy/>; Phono3py^{25,32} is available at <https://phonopy.github.io/phono3py/>; κ ALDo³⁵ is available at <https://github.com/nanotheorygroup/kaldo>.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

G.S., M.S. and D.B. conceived the ideas and developed the theory. G.S. and F.S. performed the calculations. A.C., D.C., C.M. and R.D. contributed to the codes. G.S. drafted the manuscript. D.C., C.M. and D.B. supervised the research. All authors contributed to the discussions and provided feedback on the manuscript.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

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